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Abstract book

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The decreased mean platelet volume in patients with head and neck cancer treated with radiotherapy

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Introduction: Intensity modulated radiotherapy (IMRT) technique is currently considered standard in RT treatment plans, mainly because of its ability to better limit the dose to adjacent organs at risk over three-dimensional conformal RT (3D-CRT). Recently the increasing knowledge in molecular characterization of head and neck cancer (HNSCC) opens the way for a more tailored treatment. In recent studies, altered mean platelet volume (MPV) has been associated with prognosis in different types of cancer.

Materials and methods: A retrospective analysis of total 53 patients was done who underwent IMRT (32 patients) and 3D-CRT (21 patients) for HNSCC in our institute. Patients treated with postoperative RT, total dose of 70 Gy, in both groups. Laboratory and clinical data were analysed retrospectively. Furthermore, the patients were subdivided according to cancer degree of differentiation and presence of blood vessel invasion.

Results: The percentage of recurrence after three years of patient follow-up was higher in the 3D-CRT group (28.5%) than in patients who underwent IMRT (21.8%), but the difference is not statistically significant ($p = 0.5795$). The number of platelets were statistically higher in both groups after radiotherapy. There was a drop in the MPV value after radiotherapy in both groups, but it was statistically significant only in the 3D-CRT group ($p = 0.003$). The MPV value is statistically significantly lower in patients with G3 histological grade and in group with positive tumor vascular invasion.

Conclusion: Our study shows decreased post-treatment MPV in HNSCC patients. Validation of our findings in prospective studies is im-

perative to draw firm conclusions about the role of the MPV for HNSCC prognosis after RT.

Keywords: mean platelet volume, intensity modulated radiotherapy, three-dimensional conformal radiotherapy

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